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EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON INTER-YARN FRICTION CHARACTERISTICS OF KEVLAR FABRICS WITH DIFFERENT MASS CONCENTRATIONS OF STF

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Introduction

- **High strength woven fabrics** are widely used in structural systems where high energy absorption is required, such as soft-wall casing in aero-engine containment application.
- **Shear thickening fluid (STF)** is found that it could improve and enhance the anti-impact and anti-punch performance of Kevlar fabrics, and correspondingly decrease the number of fabric layers.
- The performance of STF-Kevlar is significantly influenced by the **technological parameter** and **rheological behavior of STF**.
- The **friction characteristics** between yarns are the main factors affecting the impact resistance of high-performance fabrics.
- In the current paper, **the friction behavior** of STF-Kevlar fabrics and neat Kevlar fabrics were investigated respectively. Three types of STF of different particle concentration were prepared with nano spherical SiO₂ particles of the same diameter. The steady and **dynamic rheological properties** of three types of STF were tested for three types of STF. **Yarn pull-out testing** was conducted on the STF-Kevlar and neat Kevlar fabrics respectively with two different loading rate. The influence of STF on the friction behavior between yarns was figured out.

PREPARATION OF STF-KEVLAR FABRICS

Materials:

- nano spherical SiO_2 particles of 650nm diameter
- polyethylene glycol 200 and 400 (PEG200: PEG400=1: 2) as solvent
- Three disperse phase mass concentrations 70%, 72% and 75%

Steady rheological properties

- Testing Device: MCR301 rheometer
- Results:
 - ✓ the original viscosity and the maximum viscosity both increase with the mass concentration
 - ✓ the critical shear rate decrease with the mass concentration.
 - ✓ The critical shear rate of three types STF is about 1/s.
 - ✓ the maximum viscosity is influenced significantly by the mass concentration. The maximum viscosity can be 20 times higher when the mass concentration increases by only 5%.

PREPARATION OF STF-KEVLAR FABRICS

Dynamic rheological properties of STF

Results:

- the STF with different mass concentration all show the **reversible shear thickening and shear thinning phenomenon**.
- In the range of testing, the **loss modulus** of STF is higher than **storage modulus**, indicating the STF behaves viscous and consumes energy at a macro level.
- In the case of **shear thinning**, the storage modulus (G') decrease slightly, while the loss modulus (G'') remains unchanged.
- In case of **shear thickening**, the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') both increase. The variation of modulus with strain is similar to stress.
- The loss modulus increases with the **angular frequency** while the storage modulus increases first and decreases later.

Yarn pull-out tests of STF-Kevlar fabrics

The yarn pull-out test was carried out on **INSTRON 2344 test machine** with **maximum load bearing capacity of 2 KN**.

- Clamping the pull-out specimen on the testing machine. The length of the yarn fixed by the upper end clamp is 3 cm, and the size of the fabric fixed by the lower end clamp is 8 cm × 2 cm. The **length of the yarn sliding over the fabric is 9 cm**.
- The three previously marked yarns were pulled out from the fabric with the same loading rate of **50mm/min** for neat Kevlar and three different concentration STF-Kevlar fabrics, and the corresponding load-displacement curves were obtained.
- The pull-out tests were carried out at **loading rate of 500 mm/min** again and another set of data were obtained for 4 types of fabrics.
- The comparison of the testing fabrics before and after the pull-out test.

Test results and analysis

Force-displacement curve

The force-displacement curves have similar variation tendency:

- The **pull-out force** increase sharply to a maximum value and begin to descend slowly in a fluctuate pattern.
- The pull-out force is generated by **the friction action** between the yarn extracted and these yarns in contact with it.
- At the beginning of the pull-out test, the yarn to be pull-out contacts the maximum number of yarns in interlaced style.
- With the proceeding of pull-out test, the **extraction yarn sliding over the cross-points** one by one, causing the high frequency fluctuation in the curves.
- As **the decreasing of the yarn number in contact**, the friction force decrease gradually.
- When the yarns were **pull-out completely from the fabric**, the force decline to zero.

neat Kevlar

70wt%

72wt%

75wt%

loading rate 500 mm/min

Test results and analysis

Measurement of Friction Coefficient

The **coefficient of friction** between the warp and fill yarns can be obtained indirectly by the following equation:

$$F = C \times \text{Count}^4 \times \text{Diameter}^2 \times \text{Modulus} \times \text{Waviness} \times \text{Friction}$$

- F is the peak force during the fiber pull-out test
- C is the constant value based on the friction coefficient of the Kevlar fabric, 0.573
- Diameter is the diameter of a single fiber contained in a single yarn - 1.2×10^{-5} m
- Modulus is axial elasticity modulus of the yarn, Pa
- Waviness is the thickness of the yarn - 7×10^{-5} m
- Friction is the friction coefficient between warp and fill yarns.

Fabric type	Pull-out rate mm/min	Peak force (N)	Static friction coefficient	Dynamic friction coefficient
Neat Kevlar fabric	50	5.658	0.1612	0.0940
	50	5.932	0.1690	0.0985
	50	4.473	0.1274	0.0743
	500	3.181	0.0906	0.0528
	500	4.298	0.1225	0.0714
	500	5.102	0.1453	0.0847
70%STF-Kevlar fabric	50	10.030	0.2857	0.1666
	50	9.029	0.2572	0.1500
	50	8.523	0.2428	0.1415
	500	9.581	0.2729	0.1591
	500	9.744	0.2776	0.1618
	500	9.615	0.2739	0.1597
72%STF-Kevlar fabric	50	8.127	0.2315	0.1350
	50	6.582	0.1875	0.1093
	50	9.345	0.2662	0.1552
	500	11.678	0.3327	0.1940
	500	11.932	0.3399	0.1982
	500	11.828	0.3370	0.1965
75%STF-Kevlar fabric	50	11.931	0.3399	0.1982
	50	13.401	0.3818	0.2226
	500	12.431	0.3541	0.2065
	500	16.359	0.4660	0.2717
	500	14.346	0.4087	0.2383
	500	14.346	0.4087	0.2383

Test results and analysis

- The value of **friction coefficients of STF-Kevlar fabrics increases significantly**, reaching the percentage more than 100% and 200% at most, compared with neat Kevlar fabrics.
- With the increase of STF concentration, the friction coefficients between the warp and fill yarns of STF-Kevlar fabrics also increase significantly.
- The **yarn pull-out rate** has little effect on the friction coefficient between the yarns.

Conclusions

In the current paper, the inter-yarn friction characteristics were investigated on neat Kevlar fabric and STF-Kevlar fabrics of three different concentrations. The variation of stress-modulus and viscosity-modulus were obtained through rheological properties tests. Three types of STF-Kevlar fabrics were obtained by immersing by the prepared STF solution. The yarn pull-out tests were carried out and compared for neat Kevlar fabrics and three types of STF-Kevlar fabrics. The main conclusions were drawn as follows:

- The critical shear rate of three types STF is relatively close at about $1/s$ while the maximum viscosity is influenced significantly by the mass concentration. The maximum viscosity could be 20 times higher when the mass concentration increases by only 5%.
- The yarn pull-out force of the STF-Kevlar fabrics is much higher than neat Kevlar fabrics. The force required for the corresponding yarn to be pulled out increase with the concentration of STF increases in principle while it is barely affected by the yarn pull-out rate.
- The friction coefficients between yarns of neat Kevlar fabric is much lower than STF-Kevlar fabrics. The friction coefficients are also affected positively by the particle weight concentration. The higher the concentration of STF-Kevlar fabric, the greater the dynamic and static friction coefficients between the yarns